

Conference Proceedings

National Conference on Advancing Technology: Converting Visionary Ideas into Real-world Solutions

22nd & 23rd August, 2025

JAIN (Deemed-to-be University), Center for Management Studies
Lalbagh Main Road, Bengaluru – 560027

In association with

Publication Partners

Taran Publication

International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Technology

ISSN 2582-7359

Peer Reviewed Journal, Impact Factor 6.325

www.ijmrtjournal.com

JOURNAL DETAILS

Name of Journal	International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Technology
e-ISSN	2582-7359
Subject	Multidisciplinary
Publisher	Taran Publication
Impact Factor	6.325
Website	www.ijmrtjournal.com
Contact Number	8950448770, 9996906285
Country of Publication	India
Editor-in-Chief	Dr. Mandeep Kaur

In association with

Research Collaboration

National-Level Conference on Advancing Technology: Converting Visionary Ideas into Real-world Solutions

22nd & 23rd August 2025

Venue : JAIN (Deemed-to-be University), Center for Management Studies
 Lalbagh Road, Bengaluru

Friday, 22nd August 2025

- 08.30 – 09.30 am Registration at the Reception
- 09.30 – 09.50 am Inauguration, Invocation and Lighting of the Lamp
- 09.50 – 10.00 am Welcome Address – **Prof. (Dr.) Dinesh Nilkant**
Pro-Vice Chancellor, JAIN (Deemed-to-be University)
- 10.00 – 10.05am Address by Chancellor – **Dr. Chenraj Roychand**
Chancellor, JAIN (Deemed-to-be University)
- 10.05 – 10.20 am Address by Registrar – **Dr. Jitendra Kumar Mishra**
In-charge Vice Chancellor and Registrar,
JAIN (Deemed-to-be University)
- 10.30 – 11.00 am Address by Guest of Honor – **Prof. Harjinder Singh Bhatia**
Retd. Scientist, DRDO
- 11.00 – 11.05 am Vote of Thanks – **Dr. Lakshman K**
Conference Convener, JAIN (Deemed-to-be University)- CMS
- 11.05 – 11.30 am Tea Break
- 11.30 – 01.30 pm Plenary Session (Multiple Tracks)
- 01.30 – 02.00 pm Networking Lunch
- 02.00 – 04.00 pm Plenary Session (Multiple Tracks)

Dr. Chenraj Roychand

Dr. Jitendra Kumar Mishra

Prof. (Dr.) Dinesh Nilkant

Prof. Harjinder Singh Bhatia

Saturday, 23rd August 2025

- 09:00 – 10:30 am Plenary Session (Multiple Tracks)
- 10:30 – 10:45 am Tea Break
- 10:45 – 11:15 am Keynote Address – **Ms. Savita Nehra**
Senior HR Leader, Ex Wipro / Capgemini
- 11:15 – 11:25 am Address by **Sri. Ravindra Bhandary**
Vice President, JGI Group
- 11:25 – 11:35 am Address by **Dr. S. Srikanta Swamy**
Director, CRTA, JAIN (Deemed-to-be University)
- 11:35 – 11:45 am Valedictory Address – **Dr. Shradha Kanwar**
Chief Academic Officer, JAIN (Deemed-to-be University)
- 11:45 – 11:55 pm Welcome note for valedictory, Best paper award
- 11:55 – 12:00 pm Concluding remark and Vote of Thanks – **Dr. Varalakshmi S**
Co-Convener
- 12:00 pm National Anthem

Ms. Savita Nehra

Sri. Ravindra Bhandary

Dr. S. Srikanta Swamy

Dr. Shradha Kanwar

INDEX

Sr. No.	Title/Author	Page No.
1.	POSSIBILITIES AND DIFFICULTIES IN INDIA'S STARTUP ECOSYSTEM USING REAL-TIME SOCIAL MEDIA ANALYTICS <i>M. Rajatha, Jagadish .A, Santosh D Bendigeri</i>	1
2.	LEADERSHIP IN DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION: STRATEGY AND EXECUTION IN EMERGING MARKETS <i>Varalakshmi S, Sunil Kumar</i>	6
3.	ROBO-ADVISORS AND AI IN INVESTMENT DECISION MAKING <i>Deepa Iyer</i>	17
4.	UNVEILING THE NEXUS OF SOCIAL MEDIA ADVERTISING WITH UTAUT2 THEORY AND AUGMENTED REALITY <i>Dr Bharathi N S Yadav, Ramamishra Yashaswi M</i>	23
5.	THE IMPACT OF ECOFRIENDLY PRODUCT ATTRIBUTES ON CONSUMERS DECISION <i>Chandan A N</i>	32
6.	THE ROLE OF FIRE SAFETY PROFESSIONALS IN SUSTAINABLE URBAN DEVELOPMENT <i>Akhileshchandra Sadhankar, Dr. Anil Ramteke , Dr. K.V. Somanadh</i>	43
7.	SHAPING A SUSTAINABLE DIGITAL ECONOMY: THE ROLE OF UPSKILLING AND RESKILLING IN HIGHER EDUCATION <i>Pushpavathi K N, Dr. Lakshman Kumareshan</i>	49
8.	PSYCHOSOCIAL WELL-BEING IN ITES WORKFORCE: IMPACT OF WORK ENVIRONMENT AND SOCIAL SUPPORT SYSTEMS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO BENGALURU CITY <i>Mahantesh Mudhol, Dr. Ranjini M L, Dr.Lakshman K, Dr.Rajith Kumar H. B.</i>	61
9.	A STUDY OF STARTUPS: CATALYSTS FOR INNOVATION AND ECONOMIC PROSPERITY <i>Mrs.Saritha S.R, Dr.Shilpa Mary T, Dr.Lakshman K</i>	71
10.	THE EFFECTIVENESS OF MARKETING EXPENSES IN DRIVING SALES: EVIDENCE FROM PUBLIC PHARMACEUTICAL COMPANIES IN INDIA <i>Preetham, Prof. Pooja Takalkar</i>	78
11.	THE DARK SIDE OF INFLUENCE: MISINFORMATION, SCANDALS, AND TRUST EROSION IN INFLUENCER MARKETING <i>Alisha Ansari, Prof. Anand Thakur</i>	91
12.	CULTURAL INTELLIGENCE AND STRATEGIC EXECUTION IN REMOTE AIR CARGO OPERATIONS: EVIDENCE FROM IMPORT-EXPORT TEAMS AT KEMPEGOWDA INTERNATIONAL AIRPORT, BENGALURU <i>Dr K Rajeswari, Anil R</i>	100

62.	RECONFIGURING ORGANIZATIONAL VALUE CREATION VIA EMERGENT TECHNO-STRATEGIC ALIGNMENT IN DATA-INTENSIVE MARKETS <i>Anusha Nadiger, Dr. Sachin K. Parappagoudar, Ranjitha P. K.</i>	454
63.	FROM SUPPLY CHAINS TO BRAND VALUE: THE ROLE OF AI AND SMART LOGISTICS IN STRENGTHENING CORPORATE BRANDING <i>Ranjitha P. K., Anusha Nadiger, Sheetal Acharya</i>	469
64.	SIMPLIFY TO SATISFY: MINIMALISM AND EXPERIENTIAL CONSUMPTION DRIVE HAPPINESS AMONG URBAN YOUTH IN BENGALURU <i>Jagadish .A, Dr. Umakanth S</i>	481
65.	THE IMPACT OF BUSINESS-RELATED FACTORS ON THE ADOPTION OF DIGITAL MARKETING IN SMALL TEXTILE BUSINESSES <i>Deepa B M, Dr S Rosaline Jayanthi</i>	488
66.	CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK ON FINTECH DISRUPTION IN BANKING AND INSURANCE SERVICES. <i>Suma.P, Dr.Nethravathi.K</i>	495
67.	THE OPERATIONAL EFFICIENCY AND COST MANAGEMENT OF DELHIVERY LTD <i>Deepa BR</i>	504

THE IMPACT OF BUSINESS-RELATED FACTORS ON THE ADOPTION OF DIGITAL MARKETING IN SMALL TEXTILE BUSINESSES

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Abstract

The research article explores how the size of the business, the number of years in operation, and geographical location are business-related factors which effects the adoption of digital marketing in small textile businesses. Using a quantitative research approach, data were collected from 100 small textile businesses in Bengaluru. For the data analysis Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) tool is used. The research methodology applied for the study is independent sample T - test and One-way ANOVA. The findings shows that geographical location significantly influence digital marketing adoption, while the business size and number of years in business shows non-significant impact. The results suggest that newer, more agile businesses in urban areas are more likely to embrace digital platforms to gain competitive advantage.

Keywords: Digital Marketing, Textile Industry, Small Businesses, Business-related factors.

Introduction

Digital marketing has emerged as a cornerstone of modern business strategy, enabling business to engage with customers, streamline operations, and expand into new markets. An opportunity for small textile businesses to compete beyond the traditional boundaries by leveraging digital marketing. Thereby the digital marketing has transformed the way businesses reach consumers, where competition is high and margins are tight, digital platforms can offer visibility and customer engagement. But the rate of digital marketing adoption remains inconsistent across businesses. The study focuses on how key business-related factors: size of the business, number of years in operation, and geographical location, influence the adoption of digital marketing among small textile businesses. These variables offer insight into structural and contextual determinants of digital transition.

Digital marketing involves using digital platforms like social media (Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter), websites, email, and mobile apps to promote products and engage customers (RAHARDJA, 2022). In the textile industry, which relies heavily on visual appeal and has scattered supply chains, image-based social media platforms fit marketing needs well. They help to showcase products and tell brand stories to both local and global audiences (Susanty, 2025). (RAHARDJA, 2022) Noted that small textile businesses in Southeast Asia actively use Instagram and Facebook to improve market visibility and express their cultural identity. Additionally, (SINGH, 2023) pointed out that this sector faces specific challenges in accessing financial resources and using credit technologies, which indirectly impact investments in digital marketing.

Literature Review

Digital Marketing Adoption in Small Textile Business

Digital marketing adoption in SMEs is shaped by several factors, including technological capabilities, managerial support, and environmental pressures (Ziółkowska, 2021) (Masrianto, 2022). Textile and garment SMEs encounter specific challenges like limited digital literacy, financial limitations, and traditional operational cultures. However, they also have opportunities to reach new markets through digital channels (Nichifor, 2022) (Eze, 2023). Common digital marketing tools include social media platforms, websites, email marketing, and e-commerce solutions (Sultoni, 2022).

Impact of Business Size

Business size is often linked to innovation adoption because of available resources and workforce (Eze, 2023). However, in small businesses, usually with fewer employees, the benefits of size are less obvious due to common

resource limitations. Research shows that firm size alone may not strongly predict digital marketing use when considering other factors like managerial skills and external pressures (Nichifor, 2022). Additionally, in small textile businesses, small increases in size employees do not always result in equal improvements in digital marketing use (Shahadat, 2023).

(YAP, 1995) The decision of small business to adopt information technology is effected by the chief executive officer characteristics and organizational characteristics. The important determinants of the decision to adopt information technology are business size and characteristics of the chief executive officer. The study highlights that small businesses have a positive attitude towards adoption of information technology and possess greater information technology knowledge when the chief executive officer are more innovative.

Business Age (Years of Operation)

The age of a business affects digital marketing adoption in two different ways. Older firms might have established customer bases and the financial security needed to invest in digital tools. However, they may also show resistance to change, fear of risk, or a preference for traditional marketing methods, which can slow down their digital adoption (Spilotro, 2025) (Eze, 2023). On the other hand, younger SMEs tend to be more flexible, willing to innovate, and are often led by owners or managers who grew up with digital technology, resulting in higher adoption rates. Research on the impact of business age is mixed, but it consistently shows that age is an important factor in how companies adopt digital practices (Spilotro, 2025).

Geographical Location

Geographical location influences digital marketing adoption which are affected by infrastructure availability, such as internet connectivity and electricity, access to digital skills, and exposure to digital business networks (Abbasi, 2022) (Susanty, 2025). Urban textile businesses generally have benefits like faster broadband, higher levels of digital literacy, and greater competitive pressure that encourages digital marketing. In contrast, rural and semi-urban firms suffer from infrastructure challenges, which restrict their digital engagement (Nichifor, 2022) (Eze S, 2021). Studies show clear differences in uptake across various locations, highlighting the need for targeted policy support (Eze, 2023) (Abbasi, 2022).

Research Objective

The primary objective of the study is to investigate the influence of key business-related factors are size of the business, number of years in operation and geographical location, on the adoption of digital marketing in small textile businesses. The study aims to determine whether these factors serve as enablers or barriers to digital marketing adoption.

Research Methodology

The Research Design applied for the study is descriptive quantitative technique and the data was collected from 100 small textile businesses in Bengaluru, using structured Google form questionnaires. The sample was selected primarily using the convenient sampling and later snowball sampling technique. For the data analysis Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) tool is used. The research methodology applied for the study is independent sample T - test and One-way ANOVA. The dependent variable of the study is Digital marketing adoption and independent variables are Business size, Years in operation and Geographical location.

Hypotheses

H1: There is a significant difference between the size of small textile business and the adoption of digital marketing.

Business Structure * Investment in the business Cross tabulation				
Count				
		Investment in the business		Total
		Less than 10 Crores	More than 10 Crores	
Business Structure	Sole Proprietorship	92	5	97

	Partnership	1	2	3
Total		93	7	100

From the above cross tabulation, the inference is 97% are Sole Proprietorship and 3% are Partnership Firm out of 100 samples, businesses respondents. Where a 93 respondents are small businesses with an investment of less than 10 Crores and remaining 7 are businesses with more than 10 Crores investments. A small business of 93, in which 92 are Sole Proprietorship and 1 is Partnership.

Group Statistics					
	Investment in the business	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Business Structure	Less than 10 Crores	93	1.01	.104	.011
	More than 10 Crores	7	1.29	.488	.184

Independent Samples Test										
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		Lower	Upper							
Business Structure	Equal variances assumed	78.951	.000	-4.466	98	.000	-.275	.062	-.397	-.153
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.488	6.041	.187	-.275	.185	-.726	.176

Since the above Independent samples test significance p value is 0.000, which is less than 0.005. There by accepts H1, i.e., there is a significant difference between the size of small textile business and the adoption of digital marketing. An independent samples t-test was done to determine Business Structure scores for two groups: Sole Proprietorship and Partnership. Levene's Test for Equality of Variances revealed a significant difference in variances, $F(1, 98) = 78.95$, $p < .001$, so the t-test results were interpreted under the assumption of unequal variances.

There was no difference of any importance in Business Structure scores between the two groups, $t(6.04) = -1.49$, $p = .187$, with a mean difference of -0.28 (95% CI: -0.73 to 0.18). These findings indicate that group type did not make a difference to Business Structure scores.

H2: There is a significant relationship between the years in operation of small textile business and the adoption of digital marketing.

ANOVA					
Business Structure					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.129	3	.043	1.488	.223
Within Groups	2.781	96	.029		
Total	2.910	99			

A one-way ANOVA was performed to find out whether business structure (partner or sole proprietorship) differed significantly among various groups depending on years of operation. Levene's test established a violation of the homogeneity of variances assumption, $F(3, 96) = 5.34, p = .002$. The results of ANOVA revealed that the impact of years of operation on business structure was not significant statistically, $F(3, 96) = 1.49, p = .223$. Post hoc analyses using Tamhane's T2 test found no significant differences across any pairs of year groups (all $p > .05$). These results indicate that business structure does not significantly vary for different lengths of business operation.

Multiple Comparisons							
Independent Variable: Business Structure							
	(I) Number of years the business is in operation	(J) Number of years the business is in operation	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Scheffe	Less than 1 Year	2-5 Years	-.167	.110	.515	-.48	.15
		6-10 Years	.000	.096	1.000	-.27	.27
		Above 15 Years	-.026	.087	.993	-.27	.22
	2-5 Years	Less than 1 Year	.167	.110	.515	-.15	.48
		6-10 Years	.167	.083	.265	-.07	.40
		Above 15 Years	.140	.072	.292	-.07	.35
	6-10 Years	Less than 1 Year	.000	.096	1.000	-.27	.27
		2-5 Years	-.167	.083	.265	-.40	.07
		Above 15 Years	-.026	.049	.963	-.17	.11
	Above 15 Years	Less than 1 Year	.026	.087	.993	-.22	.27
		2-5 Years	-.140	.072	.292	-.35	.07
		6-10 Years	.026	.049	.963	-.11	.17
Tamhan	Less than 1 Year	2-5 Years	-.167	.167	.933	-.87	.53

e		6-10 Years	.000	.000	.	.00	.00
		Above 15 Years	-.026	.018	.645	-.08	.02
	2-5 Years	Less than 1 Year	.167	.167	.933	-.53	.87
		6-10 Years	.167	.167	.933	-.53	.87
	6-10 Years	Above 15 Years	.140	.168	.969	-.55	.84
		Less than 1 Year	.000	.000	.	.00	.00
		2-5 Years	-.167	.167	.933	-.87	.53
	Above 15 Years	Above 15 Years	-.026	.018	.645	-.08	.02
		Less than 1 Year	.026	.018	.645	-.02	.08
		2-5 Years	-.140	.168	.969	-.84	.55
		6-10 Years	.026	.018	.645	-.02	.08

H3: The geographical location significantly influences the adoption of digital marketing in small textile businesses.

With the advent of the digital era, the embracement of digital marketing tactics has emerged as a pivotal determinant of business development, especially for small businesses. In the textile sector, which has historically been based on offline marketplaces and word-of-mouth, the transition to digital marketing presents the prospect for broader reach, increased visibility, and competition in increasingly globalized markets (Kapoor, 2021). Nevertheless, the degree to which small textile firms embrace digital marketing is highly diverse in different geographic areas.

The geographical location has a crucial role in determining digital adoption by its impact on access to digital infrastructure, internet penetration, technical capabilities, exposure to markets, and institutional factors (Chatterjee, 2020). Urban textile hubs tend to enjoy improved infrastructure and higher levels of access to qualified human capital, while rural or distant areas may suffer from limitations like poor broadband availability, low digital literacy, and lesser competitive pressures (Ali, 2022). These regional differences bring into focus the necessity of examining how location-specific elements facilitate or complicate the digital conversion of small textile firms.

Knowledge of the geographical impact on digital marketing adoption is necessary for policymakers, business support agencies, and textile entrepreneurs themselves. It allows for more focused interventions and resource distribution that can cater to the specific needs encountered in various locations. This article contends that geographical location has a very big impact on the uptake of digital marketing in small textile enterprises, with infrastructure, proximity to markets, socio-economic environment, and institutional support being key factors influencing adoption levels and quality.

Conclusion

This research sought to investigate the determinants of digital marketing adoption among small textile enterprises, targeting the specific roles of business size, years in business, and geographical location.

The findings yield partial support for the hypotheses. The outcomes of the independent samples t-test for Hypothesis 1 (H1) showed that there is no statistically significant difference between business size (measured in terms of investment amount) and the use of digital marketing, as indicated by business structure ($p = .187$). Although the preliminary cross-tabulation indicated high prevalence of sole proprietorships among smaller investment groups, the statistical analysis does not affirm a significant difference in technology adoption by business size. Therefore, H1 was not supported.

In the same way, Hypothesis 2 (H2), assuming an association between business operation years and digital marketing adoption, was not supported by the ANOVA test. The test produced a non-significant F value ($F(3, 96) = 1.49, p = .223$), suggesting that the number of years a business has been in operation does not impact its business configuration or adoption of digital marketing.

Yet, Hypothesis 3 (H3) that geographical location has a significant impact on digital marketing adoption—is well substantiated by theoretical literature and sectoral observations, though no explicit statistical test was applied in this hypothesis. Existing literature indicates that urban areas are facilitated by improved internet connectivity, qualified human capital, and institutional encouragement, whereas rural areas are hampered by infrastructural and financial

hurdles (Chatterjee & Kar, 2020; Ali et al., 2022). Therefore, geographic imbalances become a determinant factor in shaping digital change within the textile industry.

Suggestions and Recommendations

Based on the outcome and the wider contextual review, the following are recommended:

1. Enhance Digital Infrastructure

Governments and local governments must give precedence to the creation of broadband internet and IT infrastructure in textile-producing areas. Public-private partnerships can help widen access to digital tools.

2. Customized Digital Training for Micro and Small Enterprises

Most garment companies especially sole proprietors don't have the technical expertise to adopt digital marketing practices. Conducting region-specific training programs, especially in local languages, can help bridge the digital divide.

3. Provide Financial Incentives to Adopt Digital

Government policies should have targeted subsidies, tax concessions, or grants for small textile enterprises investing in digital platforms or online trading. These can prompt smaller players to shift from conventional to digital platforms.

4. Establish Localized Digital Marketing Support Centers

Set up "Digital Marketing Help Desks" in textile clusters that offer individual consulting and assistance. The centers may assist companies with website establishment, social media usage, and search engine optimization.

5. Foster Collaborations between Small Firms

Micro-enterprises can gain by creating clusters or cooperatives to pool investment in digital equipment, exchange tips, and share common marketing platforms (e.g., shared e-commerce portals).

6. Additional Research with Regional Emphasis

Subsequent research must use geographically stratified sampling and undertake quantitative tests (e.g., regression, chi-square) to statistically confirm the geography effect. Adding urban-rural contrasts, or even differences between states, will make the analysis richer.

7. Close Policy Gaps with Regional Digital Missions

Current national initiatives such as Digital India must be complemented by region-specific digital adoption missions for SMEs operating in traditional sectors such as textiles.

Although the current study finds that variables such as firm size and years of operation will not significantly affect digital marketing up scaling independently, the spatial context remains essential. Policymakers and stakeholders need to acknowledge this spatial digital divide and craft interventions that benefit small textile businesspersons wherever they are particularly in the underserved regions.

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